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A unique European vision
for Artificial Intelligence
to fight Childhood Cancer

The gateway to a brand new
European Pediatric Cancer
Ecosystem

A set of bespoke use cases, best
practices and guidelines for
secure AI interventions

A strong, diverse community
to share knowledge and nur-
ture collaboration

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